

Novel Strategies for Maintaining Durable Global Peace: Global consensus on a shared system for raising funds for political position elections

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Abstract

National and global governance depends on political leaders. However, some individuals with good character and strong abilities are unable to participate due to a lack of sufficient funds. This indicates that the seemingly democratic and free electoral process does not truly achieve democratic freedom, making it difficult to select outstanding statesmen. In order to reduce the opacity surrounding the collection and utilization of campaign funds and facilitate the participation of talented individuals, it is necessary to creatively reform and build a global consensus on the distribution and use of campaign funds for political leaders. Candidates should transfer 40-50% of the funds raised for their campaign to a shared account designated for the same position, which will be accessible to all candidates at that level. This novel approach aims to enhance the governance capacity of countries and regions, reduce economic and financial crises, conflicts and wars, and better maintain world peace.

Keywords: war · world peace · ethnic conflict · strategy · shared account · global governance · national governance · government consensus · the UN declaration · global consensus · law · election · campaign funds · raising funds · sustainable development · politics · campaign financing

The problems caused by the lack of campaign funds

Regional, national, and global governance all rely on political leaders, who are generally elected. The success of political candidates in their campaigns depends largely on campaign funds. The election of political leaders is a significant event that captures the attention of both the national and global public. It is also a major concern in the realms of politics, economy, management, military, and strategy. However, since World War II, there has been minimal progress in terms of reforms and innovations in the field of political campaigning. Many individuals without extensive networks may have talent and political ideals, and aspire to contribute to changing the poverty situation in their region or country, as well as contributing to world peace and sustainable development. However, due to their inability to raise sufficient funds, they are unable to run for office, truly engage in politics, and realize their political ideals. In many countries, the political arena is largely controlled by interest groups (1).

Some countries lack the cultivation of younger and capable statesmen, resulting in their presidents being in their eighties or nineties (2,3). On May 10, 2006, 80-year-old left-wing candidate Giorgio Napolitano was elected President of Italy. In 2013, 87-year-old Giorgio Napolitano was re-elected as the President of Italy (2,3).

Therefore, it can be seen that the seemingly democratic and free electoral process does not actually achieve true democracy and freedom. Currently, it is challenging to identify and elect excellent politicians through the current model of fundraising and campaign expenditures, thereby providing them with the opportunity to serve in regional, national, and global governance.

In order to prevent shady aspects of campaign funding and to elect statesmen and management experts who can truly contribute to society's sustainable development, it is essential to reform the current system for distributing and using campaign funds raised by politicians.

United Nations consensus on the distribution and use of campaign funds raised

In my opinion, political figures who lead the public must have a strong spirit of sharing and overcome selfish behavior. Politicians who lack this spirit should not be allowed to participate in politics. A portion of campaign funds collected by candidates should automatically be transferred to shared accounts at the same level of competition within the country or state, for use by all candidates at that level, including himself. Banks should establish shared accounts for political candidates of different categories, such as the president or prime minister, national senator, national representative, governor, state senator, county executive, and others.

The United Nations should reach a consensus on the following: banks should only open a shared campaign funding account for different categories of political candidates at the national or regional level. For example, there should be a shared account for presidential or prime ministerial candidates, a shared account for national senators' campaign funds, a shared account for national representatives' campaign funds, a shared account for governor's campaign funds, a shared account for state legislators' campaign funds, and a shared account for county executives' campaign funds. Contributions made by the candidates themselves are excluded. Any campaign funds raised by candidates should automatically allocate 40-50% to the shared campaign funding account at the same level (national or state), which will be used by all candidates at that same level. These accounts should be managed by the government, and the staff responsible for managing the accounts should generally not extract management fees or, at most, no more than 2% per year. The other systems for raising and using funds are consistent with the existing systems in the country.

Campaign funds in the shared account should be distributed evenly among candidates for their campaign use and should not be diverted for other purposes. If a candidate engages in public lying three times or displays serious ethical misconduct during the campaign, their allocated funds will be reduced by 30%.

Five basic preconditions that new political figures should meet in election participation

Political figures can only have a comprehensive understanding of the world and effectively govern a country if they have personally experienced the lives of the lower class. Through this process, the nation can weed out politicians who cannot endure the hardships of the lower class and who only seek political enjoyment. In order to reduce global conflicts and wars, future international political stages must minimize speculators and liars. This requires a groundbreaking methodology in the selection of politically outstanding individuals with high moral character and exceptional talent.

Any candidate who uses funds from the shared account to participate in elections must meet at least five basic requirements: first, they must have high moral character and refrain from lying or deceiving the public; second, they must handle daily and international affairs in accordance with logical principles, with no obvious violations within four years; third, they should have evident political achievements from grassroots service work, notable accomplishments from their previous job roles, and better skills in coordination and management; fourth, they must have worked for a minimum of four years at the grassroots level, including at least two years as a farmer or one year as a miner or 3 years at the factory grassroots level; and fifth, they must be loyal to their marriage and family.

Government consensus on the development of excellent peacekeepers and Statesmen

From a hundred years of history in the world political arena, so-called free and democratic elections have not consistently produced outstanding politicians. Instead, they have sometimes elected individuals who have provoked or had a penchant for war. In terms of funding arrangements for the election of political figures, the United Nations, the Security Council, the World Peace Organization, or global political associations need to significantly change their thinking or adopt disruptive innovations in methodology at a higher leadership level to uphold world peace and sustainable development. If implemented, this policy will provide a new ray of hope for many young people who thought they had no chance of entering politics and making the world a better place, inspiring them with deep passion and youthful energy, while rapidly cultivating many peace fighters and running many long-term advertisements for world peace. The author believes that once this policy is implemented, more people will be willing to donate campaign funds, increasing the public's desire to participate in and voice their opinions on politics.

The changes in the distribution of campaign funds will obviously bring new and virtuous blood to the political arena of various countries while reducing the influence of investor-controlled politicians. The author believes that this will not only enhance the governance capacity and level of countries and regions around the world, reduce economic and financial crises, conflicts and wars, better safeguard world peace and sustainable development, but also prevent inexperienced and power-hungry lunatics from creating conflicts, triggering massive warfare after being appointed to political posts. It is suggested that the United Nations advocate for a conference where global political leaders gather to establish a consensus on a new model for the allocation of raising funds for political position elections during political campaigns, as well as the

establishment of shared accounts for campaign fundraising. The conference could be held in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, or other renowned locations in China such as Leiyang, Hengshan, Chenzhou, Changsha, Foshan, Guangzhou, Beijing, or Zibo, serving as a platform for fostering a UN or global political consensus. The United Nations can subsequently issue a United Nations declaration on a novel system for political fundraising, and countries around the world can modify their respective legal provisions on campaign financing.

References and Notes

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